

CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS CONCRETE AND REINFORCED CONCRETE CORROSION ANALYSIS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the corrosion process that occurs in concrete and reinforced concrete materials used in the construction industry. During the analysis, the causes of corrosion are identified and ways to eliminate them are proposed.

Keywords: concrete, aggressive environment, corrosion, building materials, carbonization.

Introduction

Mankind has been dealing with the problem of corrosion since ancient times. In ancient Egypt, metals were coated with mineral paints, and in China and Japan, varnish coatings were used. The modern theory of corrosion was proposed in 1830 by A. De la Reeve. The fight against corrosion is carried out on an international scale.

Losses caused by corrosion can be divided into two groups: direct and indirect or direct and indirect.

Direct losses include the cost of corroded items (machines, mechanisms, pipelines, roofing materials, etc.), costs for protective measures (galvanic and varnish coatings, the use of inhibitors, the construction of warehouses for storing items or equipment, and metal loss. According to experts, 10-15% of metal produced in the world is lost annually as a result of rust. Concrete and reinforced concrete products play an important role as the main building materials in the construction of industrial, civil, and transport structures and buildings. Most buildings and structures made of concrete and reinforced concrete are exposed to aggressive environments during operation and, if anti-corrosion measures are not taken, are damaged and, as a result, become unusable. This is especially true in industrial structures where metal is in contact with the external environment in liquid and gaseous forms.

In non-ferrous metallurgy, chemistry, pulp and paper, and other industries, 20-70% of general structures are exposed to various aggressive environments that cause metal corrosion. This requires the implementation of special anti-corrosion measures. For example, agricultural structures are exposed to aggressive environments consisting of organic substances. The complexity of implementing anti-corrosion measures for such structures is that many anti-corrosion agents are toxic and cannot be used in agricultural structures.

The rate and depth of corrosion of building structures depend on the aggressiveness of the environment and the extent to which the impact of the aggressive environment on the structure was taken into account during its design, construction, and operation. According to estimates by foreign experts, losses from corrosion in the construction industry amount to 1.25% of national income. These losses include the costs of repair and restoration of the structure, and losses from a decrease in the normal operating mode as a result of an increase in repairs.

The above-mentioned situations lead to an increase in labor-intensive, manual repair and restoration work. Measures for the protection of building materials and products from corrosion are aimed at one goal - to reduce all possible damage from corrosion.

To solve this issue at a technically competent and economically justified level, it is necessary to take into account the reaction of concrete and reinforcement to an aggressive environment, the individual properties and state of reinforcement of reinforced concrete products, as well as the characteristics of corrosion protection and the nomenclature of protection.

In recent years, the following work has been carried out in the study of concrete and reinforced concrete corrosion:

- a corrosion theory was created that predicts the service life of concrete structures in various aggressive environments and justifies the necessary protective measures;
- corrosion processes under the influence of sulfates were studied, as a result of which the range of sulfate-resistant Portland cement was increased;
- a complex of additives that increase corrosion resistance by changing the structure of concrete was developed;
- the rate of carbonization of concrete was studied and a quantitative theory of the process was developed. This allows us to develop a method for determining the density and stability of concrete in a carbon dioxide atmosphere, as well as a method for determining the service life of concrete;
- a method for calculating the thermodynamic stability of concrete binders operating in various environments was developed;
- concretes with polymer and other corrosion-resistant binders, as well as cement concretes impregnated with polymers, were studied;
- the resistance of concrete to water and mixed acids in liquid glass was studied and measures were proposed to increase the strength of concrete;

- data were obtained on the degree of aggressiveness of natural and various industrial environments to concrete;
- the corrosion resistance of concrete with various porous fillers has been studied;
- a system of regulatory documents to combat corrosion of concrete and reinforced concrete in construction has been developed, in particular, anti-corrosion design standards for building materials have been published.

Analysis results.

Scientific research work on combating corrosion of concrete and reinforced concrete is regulated (coordinated) by special scientific research institutions. Regulation is carried out in the following areas:

- development of the theory of corrosion of concrete and reinforced concrete;
- research on the corrosion resistance of concrete in various aggressive environments;
- study of the process of reinforcement corrosion, study of the corrosion resistance of reinforcement, development of means of its protection;
- research on the operation of reinforced concrete structures in various aggressive environments and the creation of corrosion-resistant structures;
- protection of reinforced concrete structures with varnishes, paints, and polymer film coatings;
- technical and economic assessment of structural protection;
- improvement of corrosion testing methods.

Summary

Thus, a scientific and practical basis has been created for obtaining long-lasting concrete and reinforced concrete structures. In many countries, the design of corrosion protection of building structures is standardized at the state level. In the design of buildings and structures, there is a section on corrosion protection of structures. Special design organizations are engaged in the design of this section.

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